

Dissolved methane in soil solution

H. U. Neue, R. Wassmann, R. S. Lantin, M. C. Alberto, and J. B. Aduna. IRRI

Methane that is produced but does not escape into the atmosphere remains entrapped in the soil. This entrapped CH₄ may be oxidized, reducing net CH₄ emission to the atmosphere. Determining the amount of soil-entrapped CH₄ is time-consuming and laborious.

An alternative method is to determine the amount of CH₄ dissolved in soil solution. Floodwater and soil solutions at different depths were sampled using porous tubing. About 5-ml samples were collected in 10-ml vacutainers. The samples were shaken vigorously for 30 s and headspace gas was analyzed for dissolved CH₄. Field sampling was done weekly in plots planted to IR72 and treated with urea (low C input) and organic amendment (high C input).

The dynamics of dissolved CH₄ in soil solution over time followed the same pattern as that of soil-entrapped CH₄. A close linear relationship exists between dissolved CH₄ and entrapped CH₄ ($r = 0.916^{**}$). This allows monitoring entrapped CH₄ using the easier measurement of dissolved CH₄.

Dissolved CH₄ remained at very low levels at low C input during the early growth stages (Fig. 1). Organic amendment at high C input increased dissolved CH₄ tenfold (Fig. 2). At later growth stages, dissolved CH₄ started to increase (Fig. 1, 2). The dynamics of CH₄ production rate at affected by C input was similar to that of dissolved CH₄.

Dissolved CH₄ in the floodwater was negligible. The concentration of dissolved CH₄ in the soil solution increased with increasing depth below the soil-water interface. Maximum concentrations were recorded at 15 cm (the deepest layer sampled) (Fig. 1, 2). Methane movement from this depth was hindered by the plow pan, and the lower soil temperatures decreased CH₄ solubility. ■

CH₄ fluxes (mg/m² per h)

CH₄ (μg/m² per s)

Soil-entrapped CH₄ can be released into the atmosphere as a result of soil disturbances, such as puddling, harrowing, transplanting, weeding, fertilizer/pesticide application, and harvesting. Even if cultural practices do not disturb fields, up to 90% of the CH₄ released into the atmosphere is emitted through the aerenchyma of the rice plant.

In a field experiment using micro-meteorological techniques in combination with a tunable diode laser, CH₄ emission greatly increased during

1. Effect of soil drying on methane fluxes. IRRI.

2. Effect of weeding on methane emission from ricefield. IRRI, 1992 DS.

weeding (Fig. 2). The emission declined to previous levels after weeding. Cultural practices may account for 10-20% of the overall seasonal CH₄ emission. ■

1. Changes in dissolved CH₄ under low C input.

2. Changes in dissolved CH₄ under high C input.

Ebullition of methane

H. U. Neue, R. Wassmann, R. S. Lantin, M. C. Alberto, and J. B. Aduna, IRRI

Up to 90% of the CH₄ released into the atmosphere from ricefields is attributed to the rice plant, but another release mechanism is ebullition as gas bubbles. Ricefields are usually prepared flooded with at least 4 wk passing before rice is transplanted. If bare mud is flooded, CH₄ is entrapped in the soil, and ebullition becomes the only major pathway for CH₄ release. Cultural practices during the

growing period enhance ebullition of soil-entrapped CH₄.

To quantify the contribution of CH₄ ebullition to total fluxes, we installed Plexiglas boxes between rice hills and measured the collected gas after 24 h throughout the growing season. We monitored CH₄ ebullition and total fluxes in plots planted to IR72 and treated with mineral fertilizers and organic amendments.

1. Variability of methane in urea plot.

Methane ebullition varied greatly in all plots (Fig. 1). The variability increased as the growing season progressed. Ebullition is higher during the day than at night and the seasonal pattern was similar to that of emission. Organic amendments increased the ebullition of CH₄ (Fig. 2).

The maximum amount of CH₄ ebullition was observed 2 wk after flooding the soil, followed by a decrease during the crop's vegetative growth. Ebullition increased again during the reproductive phase, with a final peak at harvest. Ebullition contributed 20% of the total CH₄ emission. ■

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